

Infosheet: steppic Biogeographic Region

Based on NaturaConnect data

Background

Biogeographical regions are important regional delineation used in the Habitats Directive (92/43/EEC) and other European and international Conventions (Bern Convention). The Steppic region covers 916197.16 kmš land area, with protected areas currently spanning 0.87 Across variants the NaturaConnect analysis suggest to expand overall protected area coverage up to 1.13 in the Steppic region.

■ Expansion Strict PA
 ■ Expansion PA
 ■ Existing Strict PA
 ■ Existing PA
 ■ Unprotected Areas

Figure: Existing and proposed consensus expansion priorities by the NaturaConnect project.

Performance Indicators

The NaturaConnect project has identified priority areas for expanding protected area networks across Europe to better conserve biodiversity. Each region and the proposed expansion areas are evaluated through a set of 'performance' indicators that reflect either potential benefits or risks of additional conservation or restoration action in these areas.

Performance indicators for current (inner polygon) and proposed expansion areas (outer polygon).

Relative difference in indicator values of target region (red) relative to other regions (grey points). Text indicates the difference in indicator value between the target region and the mean across all regions.

Source: International Institute for Applied Systems Analysis

Key recommendations

- Expansion of protected areas to cover at least 30% of the land area is recommended to effectively conserve biodiversity.
- The steppic biogeographic region has significant potential for expanding strict protected areas.
- Connectivity between existing protected areas should be prioritized to enhance ecological networks and facilitate species movement.

📍 Explore both maps and data in detail on our [NaturaConnector](#) platform.

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